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Architecture on Mixed-Mode Fracture Toughness for Woven S-
Glass-Epoxy Composites

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Characterization Effect of Matrix, Fiber Sizing, and Weave Architecture on Mixed-Mode Fracture Toughness for Woven S-Glass-Epoxy Composites

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Motivation

In most of the structural applications the Composites are in general subjected to **events that induce complex, mixed-mode interlaminar stresses** leading to delamination

The resistance to delamination under such conditions is heavily governed by:

- **Sizing:** } The chemical nature of the fiber-matrix interface (*alters fiber matrix bond strength*)
- **Matrix:** } Resistance offered to matrix cracking and yielding
- **Architecture:** The mechanical constraints and reinforcement offered by the fiber layout (*modifies crack path, stress redistribution and through thickness reinforcement*)

Objective

- To investigate the fracture behavior of composite laminates under **mixed-mode bending (MMB)** loading for different:

- **Resin system**
- **Sizing**
- **Fabric Architecture**

Fabric	Resin	MMB Ratio (G_{II}/G_{Total})	RVE Size (mm)
463 PW	RDL-RDC	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	10
933 PW	RDL-RDC	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	10
933 8HS	RDL-RDC	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	3.5
463 PW	SC-15	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	10
933 PW	SC-15	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	10
933 8HS	SC-15	0.25, 0.5, 0.75	3.5

The fiber volume fraction (FVF) for each material system was ~50%

- To determine G_I & G_{II} components of energy release rate at different **mix mode ratios**.
- To analyze the influence of material systems on the **R-curve behavior**.
- To develop and compare **failure envelopes** for the various material systems studied.

Camera Setup

Back Camera

5 Megapixel camera on the back
FOV_2 (Behind): ~57 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$
Crack propagation

Front Camera

5 Megapixel camera on the front
FOV_2 (Front): ~10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$
Crack propagation

G_I & G_{II} Calculations

ASTM D6671/D6671M – 22

c = Lever Length

$$c = \frac{12\beta^2 + 3\alpha + 8\beta\sqrt{3\alpha}}{36\beta^2 - 3\alpha} L$$

α = Mode mixture transformation parameter

$$\alpha = \frac{1 - \frac{G_{II}}{G}}{\frac{G_{II}}{G}} = \frac{G}{G_{II}} - 1$$

β = crack length correction parameter for mixed mode

$$\beta = \frac{a + \chi h}{a + 0.42\chi h}$$

χ = crack length correction parameter,

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}}{11G_{13}} \left\{ 3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{1 + \Gamma} \right)^2 \right\}}$$

Γ = transverse modulus correction parameter

$$\Gamma = 1.18 \frac{\sqrt{E_{11}E_{22}}}{G_{13}}$$

Input Parameters (PW)

a (mm)	30
E_{11} (MPa)	26500
E_{22} (MPa)	26500
G_{13} (MPa)	2140
L (mm)	60
h (mm)	2.4-2.6

$$G_I = \frac{12P^2 (3c - L)^2}{16b^2h^3L^2E_{I_f}} (a + \chi h)^2$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 (c + L)^2}{16b^2h^3L^2E_{I_f}} (a + 0.42\chi h)^2$$

$$G = G_I + G_{II}$$

$$E_{I_f} = \frac{8(a_o + \chi h)^3 (3c - L)^2 + [6(a_o + 0.42h\chi)^3 + 4L^3] (c + L)^2}{16L^2bh^3 \left(\frac{1}{m} - C_{sys} \right)}$$

Load Displacement- Cyclic Loading

$G_{II}/G_{Total} = 0.25$

$G_{II}/G_{Total} = 0.50$

$G_{II}/G_{Total} = 0.75$

Cyclic testing is essential for :

- Measuring crack growth resistance curves (R-curves)
- Monitoring compliance changes with crack growth

These tests yield much richer data than monotonic loading, especially when studying materials with toughening mechanisms, plastic zone effects, or bridging phenomena.

Fracture Toughness Resistance-Curve

$$y = u \cdot \exp(-\exp(-k(x-x_c)))$$

u = saturation/plateau value

k = growth rate parameter

x_c = inflection point of curve

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2}{N}}$$

x_i = Measured G values

μ = G value from fitted data

N = Total number of G values

T-Test was done in the plateau region to identify if the curves are statistically different

Main Toughening Mechanisms Contributing to R-Curve Behavior in Composites

Mechanism	Micrographs	Mode I ($G_{II}/G_T = 0$)	Mixed Mode ($G_{II}/G_T = 0.25$ to 0.75)	Mode II ($G_{II}/G_T = 1.0$)
Fiber Bridging		Noticeable	May reduce in extent as shear increases	Limited
Secondary Crack Formation		Frequently observed (in certain weave architecture)	Enhanced due to combination of modes	Present (in certain weave architecture)
Interfacial Debonding		Limited	Appears more frequently	Tends to be more evident
Interlaminar Shearing/Sliding				Tends to be more
Mechanical Interlocking				es significant
Crack Deflection/Migration				d

Once the effect of these mechanism saturates the curve plateau

Parameters to assess the Fracture Resistance of Different Material System

1. G_I and G_{II} values in plateau region and their statistical difference:

- The **plateau** indicates that the material has **engaged all its available toughening mechanisms** (fiber bridging, pull-out, matrix toughening, etc.).
- Material's true or maximum resistance** to steady-state crack growth is reached.

2. Crack length at which R-curve plateau and the energy absorbed from initiation to plateau (ΔG)

- The R-curve represents the material's resistance to crack extension. A **longer/gradually rising R-curve** means the **material continues to toughen as the crack grows**. More energy is required for the crack to propagate which means **more fracture resistance and greater damage tolerance**

$$\Delta G_{I/II} = G_{I/II(\text{plateau})} - G_{I/II(\text{initiation})}$$

Effect of Resin

Table: G_I , G_{II} , R-curve plateau (crack length) for mode I and mode II components for 933 PW RDL-RDC & SC-15, 463 PW RDL-RDC & SC-15 subjected to MMB

G_{II}/G_T			G_I (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_I (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack length R-curve at Plateau (mm)	ΔG_I $G_{I(\text{plateau})} - G_{I(\text{initiation})}$ (kJ/m ²)	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack length R-curve at Plateau (mm)	ΔG_{II} $G_{II(\text{plateau})} - G_{II(\text{initiation})}$ (kJ/m ²)
0.25	933 PW	RDL-RDC	0.46	1.42	0.10	20	0.96	0.16	0.49	0.05	20	0.33
		SC-15	0.32	1.16	0.15	15	0.84	0.12	0.42	0.03	20	0.30
	463 PW	RDL-RDC	0.43	1.30	0.08	22.5	0.87	0.18	0.46	0.03	22.5	0.28
		SC-15	0.39	1.20	0.10	15	0.81	0.12	0.40	0.03	15	0.28
0.50	933 PW	RDL-RDC	0.37	1.22	0.10	17.5	0.85	0.37	1.27	0.11	17.5	0.90
		SC-15	0.33	1.05	0.02	12.5	0.72	0.33	1.09	0.02	12.5	0.76
	463 PW	RDL-RDC	0.28	0.97	0.06	15	0.69	0.29	1.02	0.06	15	0.73
		SC-15	0.35	0.88	0.08	15	0.53	0.35	0.88	0.08	15	0.53
0.75	933 PW	RDL-RDC	0.22	0.67	0.06	20	0.45	0.58	2.09	0.18	15	1.51
		SC-15	0.25	0.68	0.05	20	0.43	0.75	2.11	0.16	20	1.36
	463 PW	RDL-RDC	0.22	0.57	0.02	15	0.35	0.65	1.79	0.05	12.5	1.14
		SC-15	0.19	0.46	0.01	15	0.27	0.55	1.42	0.05	15	0.87

Summary of Observation – Effect of Resin

- The RDL-RDC resin shows **similar/higher fracture resistance in plateau region** across **all mixed mode ratios** and both **sizing (463 & 933)**.

T-Test (Both Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) Component)				T-Test (Both Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) Component)			
	0.25 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.5 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.75 933 PW RDL-RDC		0.25 463 PW SC-15	0.5 463 PW SC-15	0.75 463 PW SC-15
933 PW SC-15	Different	Different	Similar	463 PW RDL-RDC	Similar	Different	Different

- For RDL-RDC resin the R-curve plateau and ΔG is **longer/higher or comparable** to SC-15 which likely reflects **stable crack growth** and **better energy absorption capacity**

* RDL-RDC was developed by Huntsman as a replacement for SC-15, offering similar properties but with a higher glass transition temperature (T_g). Since RDL-RDC exhibits comparable or superior fracture resistance across all mixed-mode ratios, *the influence of sizing and fabric architecture is analyzed only for the RDL-RDC system.*

High shear (Mode II dominant): It appears interface becomes the key driver.

- If sizing-matrix interface is strong (Sizing 933), matrix type might not matter
- If interface strength varies with matrix (Sizing 463), matrix type probably matters

Effect of Sizing

Table: G_I , G_{II} , R-curve plateau (crack length) for mode I and mode II components for 933 PW RDL-RDC and 463 PW RDL-RDC subjected to MMB

G_{II}/G_T		G_I (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_I (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack Length at R-curve Plateau (mm)	ΔG $G_{I(plateau)} - G_{I(initiation)}$ (kJ/m ²)	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack Length at R-curve Plateau (mm)	ΔG $G_{II(plateau)} - G_{II(initiation)}$ (kJ/m ²)	G_{Total} (kJ/m ²)
0.25	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.46	1.42	0.10	20	0.96	0.16	0.49	0.05	20	0.33	1.91
	463 PW RDL-RDC	0.43	1.30	0.08	22.5	0.87	0.18	0.46	0.03	22.5	0.28	1.76
0.50	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.37	1.22	0.10	17.5	0.85	0.37	1.27	0.11	17.5	0.9	2.49
	463 PW RDL-RDC	0.28	0.97	0.06	15	0.69	0.29	1.02	0.06	15	0.73	1.99
0.75	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.22	0.67	0.06	20	0.45	0.58	2.09	0.18	15	1.51	2.76
	463 PW RDL-RDC	0.22	0.57	0.02	15	0.35	0.65	1.79	0.05	12.5	1.14	2.36

T-Test (Both Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) Component)

	0.25 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.5 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.75 933 PW RDL-RDC
463 PW RDL-RDC	Similar	Different	Different

Summary of Observation-Effect of Sizing

- Compared to **463 sizing** the **933 sizing** shows **comparable ($G_{II}/G_T=0.25$)** or **superior fracture resistance ($G_{II}/G_T=0.50$ & **0.75**)** in **plateau region**
- For **933 sizing** the **R-curve plateau rise is longer or comparable to 463 sizing** which reflects **stable crack growth** and **improved energy absorption capacity**

At low shear (Mode I dominant), both 933 and 463 perform similarly. But as **Mode II increases**, **933 PW shows higher fracture resistance** due to:

- **Prolonged activation of toughening mechanisms: Longer and more stable R-curve plateau**
- **Higher energy absorption: most likely through interfacial sliding and pull-out**

This makes 933 PW likely more suitable for **mixed-mode or shear-dominant structural applications** where **damage tolerance and fracture resistance** are critical.

Effect of Architecture

Table: G_I , G_{II} , R-curve plateau (crack length) for mode I and mode II components for 933 PW RDL-RDC vs 933 8HS RDL-RDC subjected to MMB

G_{II}/G_T		G_I (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_I (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack length at R-curve Plateau (mm)	ΔG $G_{I(plateau)} - G_{I(initiation)}$ (kJ/m ²)	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Initiation	G_{II} (kJ/m ²) Plateau	SD (σ)	Crack length at R-curve Plateau (mm)	ΔG $G_{II(plateau)} - G_{II(initiation)}$ (kJ/m ²)	G_{Total} (kJ/m ²)
0.25	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.46	1.42	0.10	20	0.96	0.16	0.49	0.05	20	0.33	1.91
	933 8HS RDL-RDC	0.59	1.01	0.15	20	0.42	0.20	0.35	0.05	20	0.15	1.36
0.50	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.37	1.22	0.10	17.5	0.85	0.37	1.27	0.11	17.5	0.9	2.49
	933 8HS RDL-RDC	0.42	0.85	0.05	5	0.43	0.33	0.92	0.06	5	0.59	1.77
0.75	933 PW RDL-RDC	0.22	0.67	0.06	20	0.45	0.58	2.09	0.18	15	1.51	2.76
	933 8HS RDL-RDC	0.30	0.55	0.08	10	0.26	0.88	1.78	0.24	10	0.90	2.34

T-Test (Both Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) Component)

	0.25 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.5 933 PW RDL-RDC	0.75 933 PW RDL-RDC
933 8HS RDL-RDC	Different	Different	Similar

Needs further analysis as the crack growth is highly unstable, not enough data points for correct curve fit

Summary of Observation-Effect of Architecture

The PW weave consistently absorbs more energy than 8HS :

- **Due to its fabric architecture** which leads to more **energy dissipation through higher mechanical interlocking, crack path deflection, secondary crack formation**

The R-curve of 8HS is shorter and rises more steeply initially but reaches plateau earlier, especially in shear-dominated conditions:

- **Rapid saturation of toughening mechanisms like fiber bridging or crack deflection**
- Under shear, cracks tend to **propagate along fiber-matrix interfaces**. The **smoother, less interlaced/overlapping structure of 8HS** provides **less resistance** to interfacial crack growth. Hence, **shorter R-curve plateau and lower G_{II} values**

Mixed Mode Failure Envelope

The G_I vs G_{II} values measured from the R-curve for three different mixed mode ratio were extrapolated using linear fit to obtain pure mode values (Mode I and Mode II) for each crack length

R-curves for Pure Mode I & II (Extrapolated data)

R-curve was obtained for pure mode extrapolated values

R-Curve fit

$G_{IC/IIIC} = a * \exp(-\exp(-k(\Delta a - X_c)))$	G_{IC}	G_{IIIC}
a (saturation/plateau value)	1.72	3.60
k (growth rate parameter)	0.16	0.22
X_c (inflection point of curve)	0.58	1.16

Creating a Master Mixed-Mode Envelope

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}(\Delta a)} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}(\Delta a)} = 1$$

$$G_{IC}(\Delta a) = 1.72 * \exp(-\exp(-0.16(\Delta a - 0.58))) \text{ at } G_{II} = 0$$

$$G_{IIC}(\Delta a) = 3.60 * \exp(-\exp(-0.22(\Delta a - 1.16))) \text{ at } G_{IC} = 0$$

Δa	$G_{IC}(\Delta a)$	$G_{IIC}(\Delta a)$
0	0.57	0.99
2.5	0.82	1.71
5	1.05	2.34
7.5	1.24	2.81
10	1.38	3.12
12.5	1.48	3.31
15	1.56	3.43
17.5	1.61	3.50
20	1.64	3.54
22.5	1.67	3.57
25	1.69	3.58
27.5	1.70	3.59
30	1.70	3.59

Converting Master Envelope to Standard Mixed Mode Envelope

Resistance-Curves (933 PW RDL-RDC)

R-curve obtained from the mixed-mode envelope for different ratio's most of which were not experimentally tested

Master Mixed Mode Envelope for 933 & 463 PW RDL-RDC

Standard Mixed-Mode Envelopes for 933 & 463 PW RDL-RDC

Conclusions

1. Resin Performance

- I. RDL-RDC demonstrates **comparable/superior fracture resistance** in the plateau region across all mode mixities ($G_{II}/G_{Total} = 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$) and both fabric sizings (PW 463 and PW 933).
- II. RDL-RDC exhibits **longer or higher R-curve plateau** and ΔG values compared to SC-15, indicating **more stable crack growth** and **greater energy absorption** capability.

2. Effect of Fabric Sizing

- I. PW 933 shows **comparable fracture resistance at 0.25 ratio** and **superior resistance at 0.50 and 0.75 ratios** compared to PW 463.
- II. The R-curve plateau for PW 933 is **longer or comparable** to PW 463, suggesting **improved toughness** and **enhanced crack stability**.

3. PW vs 8HS Fabric Architecture

- I. **PW weave consistently absorbs more fracture energy** than 8HS due to:

1. Greater **mechanical interlocking**
2. Enhanced **crack path deflection**
3. Increased **secondary crack formation**

These mechanisms contribute to higher energy dissipation and improved resistance.

4. Created a **master curve** for **mixed-mode failure** including **R-curve** effects

Fracture toughness values for any mixed-mode ratio (G_{II}/G_{Total} from 0 to 1) and crack length can be estimated using experimental data from three tested ratios: ($G_{II}/G_{Total} = 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$).

This enables the estimation of fracture toughness for mixed-mode conditions that are not experimentally accessible due to limitations in the test setup—specifically, when the lever length (c) is less than three times the span length (L).

Future Work

As we go from Mode I (opening mode) dominant mixed mode ratio to Mode II (Shear mode) dominant ratio the contribution to fracture resistance as a result of mechanical interlocking due to fiber architecture (PW) will be studied in detail

- A combination of normal and shear movement could affect the friction/resistance offered.
- If normal opening > half tow thickness, less resistance in shear movement

Christopher Meyer, Ph.D. Dissertation 2022

CTOD-Normal and Shear

Start of Loading

End of Loading

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